

Immanuel Kant's idea of people's power

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Abstract

The article analyzes the fact that Immanuel Kant put forward the idea of populist power in social relations, the content of this idea is that the legislative power should only express the will of the people, and this will of the people should be the source of laws in a legal state.

Key words: populism, desire, right, freedom, power.

Аннотация

В статье анализируется тот факт, что Иммануил Кант выдвинул идею народнической власти в общественных отношениях, содержание этой идеи состоит в том, что законодательная власть должна лишь выражать волю народа, и эта воля народа должна быть источником законов в правовом государстве.

Ключевые слова: народничество, желание, право, свобода, власть.

Аннотация

Мақолада Иммануил Кантнинг ижтимоий муносабатларга доир халқчил ҳокимият ғоясини илғари сурганлиги, ушбу ғоянинг мазмуни қонун чиқарувчи ҳокимият фақат умумхалқ хоҳиш-иродасини ифодалаш шартлиги

ва халқнинг мана шу хоҳиш-иродаси ҳуқуқий давлатдаги қонунларнинг манбааси бўлиши лозимлиги таҳлил этилган.

Калит сўзлар: халқчиллик, хоҳиш-ирода, ҳуқуқ, эркинлик, ҳокимият.

Immanuel Kant, who laid the foundation stone for the formation of the German classical philosophy of the new era, puts forward the idea of popular power while analyzing social relations. The essence of this idea is that "Legislative power must express only the will of the people" and "such a will of the people should be the source of laws in a legal state." These interrelated and complementary considerations may not surprise many people today. After all, these or similar thoughts are often expressed by ordinary citizens and heads of state, and are recognized as the main principle that serves the development of countries. We would like to say that this phrase, which was introduced as a slogan, has become an important principle of state and society construction for most countries. However, several hundred years ago, in the conditions in which Immanuel Kant lived, it was practically impossible for him to be recognized by the government and applied to the processes of the state and society. After all, at that time, all the countries of the world were ruled by monarchs, that is, sole rulers, kings, emperors, and they protected the interests of the upper classes, feudal lords and capitalists. Laws and regulations in the countries were created directly based on their demands and interests and served them. The interests of the general public were left behind. Only the advanced people of their time, like Kant, were able to say that such a situation is wrong and put forward the ideas that the state should

take into account the will of the entire people, not just the upper class, and the laws of the state should also serve the interests of the people. The heads of state and the ruling classes, in turn, resisted the implementation of these ideas. Because the realization of such ideas necessitated giving freedom and liberty to the people. In turn, the emergence of this situation was unpleasant for the rulers. The reason is that the people who have freedom and freedom realize their rights and do not want to obey the rulers and always serve others. They begin to demand participation in the administration of the state and the adoption of laws. They begin to fight for equal distribution of material and spiritual wealth in the society for everyone, to ensure equal decent life for everyone. Representatives of the ruling class, who knew well what the outcome of this struggle would be, prevented it in various ways. These obstacles are made through various forms, methods and means. It is true that the main command of the ruling class to keep the people in obedience was the coercive apparatus of the state, that is, the army, the police and other means of using force. However, in addition to these, ideological-ideological methods were also used. In such ideas and ideologies, the greatness of the rulers, the eternal existence of classes, including the rich and the poor, that is, social inequality, the fact that this order will not change, the need for the upper class to rule, and the lower class to submit to them, the ownership of property and the management of the state are beyond their reach. opposition to the laws established by the rulers was evaluated as blasphemy, disobedience, impudence. In particular, the fact that he is not ready to manage the country has been poured into the ears of the people.

However, Kant "rejects the opinion of the German serfs that the nation is not yet ripe for freedom." Because Kant understood that the serfs, who were considered feudal landowners, advanced such conclusions for their own benefit. It is worth noting that the question of when a nation is ripe for freedom has been discussed in post-Kant times and is still controversial. Let's not go far, let's turn to the era of renewed Uzbekistan. It's no secret that after the change of the head of state in 2016, radical changes took place in Uzbekistan's socio-economic, political-legal, spiritual-educational and other spheres. Let's turn our attention to the political and legal sphere. First of all, we must admit that there have been unprecedented innovations in this area. In particular, significant work was done on the issue of raising people's political and legal consciousness and culture, as a result of which our people learned to know their rights and fight for these rights. Censorship was put an end to, and freedom of speech in the press was ensured. The existing problems in the society, which have been hidden for years, began to be openly discussed. No sector is left out of this process, whether it is law enforcement, government, health, or the entire system of pre-school, public education, and higher education. After all, the wind of updates and changes is blowing in all areas. By itself, these processes arouse the consciousness of our people. It certainly had an effect on his thinking. After all, we would not be wrong to say that there is a huge difference between the people of today and the people of four or five years ago. However, on the eve of the beginning of those great historical shifts, after that, opinions were expressed and even now are being expressed, saying that "our

people are not ready for such freedoms yet." Supporters of these ideas compare our society with other societies in order to prove their point of view and confuse them with words such and such. However, they forget one thing that every society, I mean every country, has a different way of development. Then, those now relatively developed societies did not reach their current level of development all at once. Maybe they went through certain stages of development before reaching this level. And there were certain mistakes and shortcomings along the way. Therefore, we will never be ready for freedom if we conclude that "our people are not yet ready for such freedoms" and "we will be ready when we reach the level of those developed societies". Because a person cannot be ready for freedom without feeling freedom. To feel freedom, it is necessary to achieve it. Simply put, people should be given freedom first, and then it is appropriate to make them ready for freedom, or rather, to be worthy of freedom. After a person is given freedom, his ability to be free and live as a full-fledged citizen in a civil society depends on a number of factors, in particular, education and training. He is nobody without education. It should be noted that only educated people can educate a person." The correctness of this opinion was confirmed several times both in Kant's time and in later periods. Educational processes take place in society. The main link of society is the family. After that, educational institutions at all levels, communities of different levels, streets, neighborhoods, villages, towns, districts, cities, regions, and finally the population of the entire country will cover the formation of that state society. In fact, "the two inventions of people are the most difficult: for

example, the art of management and education". Kant did not equate management and education in his reasoning. At first glance, these two concepts seem far from each other, unrelated. There are those who believe that governance is a process related to the management of the country and the activities of rulers, while education is the work of parents and teachers. But, on the surface, it seems so. The connection between these two concepts is that management is education, and education is management. Above, we talked about education, its complex and conflicting aspects. Now let's analyze the concept of management, management. First of all, it should be noted that the concept of management is a very broad and complex concept. When it comes to governance, most people usually think of governing the country. But the management of countries is the highest, highest level of management. Until then, we must not forget that even at the lower levels there are specific manifestations and forms of management. Management is ten different ways to deal with ten people, and a hundred different ways to deal with a hundred people. Explaining to those who do not understand, that is, requires constant engagement in educational work. But this is not an easy process. For this, it is desirable that managers have organization, knowledge, humanity, strictness, justice, politeness, strong will, patience and a number of other characteristics. Because, at the same time, managers are required to fulfill assigned tasks, achieve future goals, and coordinate these processes in the interests of people. We can draw such a conclusion from the above-mentioned points. The process of management in the system of social relations is very complex, therefore, it is a very responsible

social phenomenon. The effectiveness of management depends on a number of factors, in particular, the educational process. Management is a continuous, ongoing education. This education is carried out in the whole society and in different levels of communities that are part of it. At this point, it is difficult to create a single principle of education that is correct for everyone, except for the partial generalization of certain aspects. Because there are as many people in the world as there are different types of character. The same conclusion can be drawn about communities made up of different people. There are no communities whose conditions are exactly the same. Therefore, each of them requires an individual approach to itself. Individual approach is one of the main rules of education. Or else, let's go back to the family rule we mentioned earlier. We would like to express an opinion on this topic. This idea is not new to many people.

Literature.

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